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STRATEGIC GROWTH OF GLOBAL COMPANIES IN CONTEMPORARY ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: This article examines strategies for the expansion of international companies in today's environment. It investigates the core principles underlying the development strategies of these companies in the modern context. Additionally, it analyzes the initiatives of the "Uztekstilprom" association and proposes practical recommendations to improve its development strategy.

Key words: Corporate strategy, operational strategy, market share, enterprise resources, growth demand intensive, strategy offensive.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bugungi sharoitda xalqaro kompaniyalarni kengaytirish strategiyalarini ko'rib chiqadi. U zamonaviy kontekstda ushbu kompaniyalarning rivojlanish strategiyalari asosidagi asosiy tamoyillarni o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, "O'zto'qimachilik sanoat" uyushmasi tashabbuslarini tahlil qilib, rivojlanish strategiyasini takomillashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Korporativ strategiya, operatsion strategiya, bozor ulushi, korxonalar resurslari, o'sish talabi intensiv, hujumkor strategiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются стратегии расширения международных компаний в современных условиях. В ней исследуются основные принципы, лежащие в основе стратегий развития этих компаний в современных условиях. Кроме того, в ней анализируются инициативы ассоциации «Узтекстильпром» и предлагаются практические рекомендации по совершенствованию ее стратегии развития.

Ключевые слова: Корпоративная стратегия, операционная стратегия, доля рынка, ресурсы предприятия, рост спроса, интенсивная стратегия, наступательная стратегия.

INTRODUCTION

With the globalization of the world economy, the role of domestic businesses as crucial players in the global market has significantly increased. Many local companies, driven by their rapid growth and accumulated economic resources over recent decades, aim to join the ranks of major global players. However, these companies confront an environment marked by rising uncertainty, including swiftly changing international markets, intensified competition, strict regulatory frameworks, and notable shifts in the global economy.

As a result, domestic firms understand the necessity of crafting strategies to expand their operations abroad, not only to boost shareholder value but also to position themselves as active participants in the international arena. To achieve this goal, it is essential to thoroughly analyze strategic options amid fierce competition from foreign rivals, all while managing limited time and resources.

The array of strategic choices available, combined with these constraints, underscores the need for an effective international strategy. Therefore, examining a company's international strategy continues to be a critical and urgent topic

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

M. Porter[1] explains in his work strategic approaches aimed at building competitive advantage. It is shown that global companies can achieve superiority by effectively managing the value chain, product or service differentiation, as well as competing on price, taking into account the specifics of the competitive environment. This work is a theoretical basis for methods of expanding enterprises and maintaining competitiveness in modern market conditions.

C. Bartlett and S. Ghoshal[2] developed a “transnational” management model of large corporations operating internationally, and show directions for successful operation in different market and cultural conditions. The book emphasizes the need to maintain a balance between the company’s local market requirements and global coordination when developing a global strategy. The authors illustrate the complexities of global expansion with practical examples and provide relevant guidelines for managers and researchers.

M. Hitt, R. Ireland and R. Hoskisson[3] in their research deeply cover the theoretical foundations of corporate strategy and methods of their practical application. The book explains how global companies should pay attention to innovation, strategic resource allocation, social responsibility and other modern factors in the process of strategic decision-making. It also shows the importance of developing corporate entrepreneurship and using in-depth analytical tools to maintain competitiveness.

M. Peng[4] provides a comprehensive analysis of the main theories of global strategy, in particular, the institutional environment, the entry strategies of multinational companies and the selection of resources. The author shows how companies should focus on combining local and global approaches to marketing, production, personnel policy and financial planning in order to achieve success in different markets. This work provides important practical recommendations on taking into account political and economic risks in global expansion.

In his book, G. Yip[5] presents theoretical and methodological foundations for the strategy of global companies and strengthening their competitive advantage at the global level. The author emphasizes the need for in-depth study of the characteristics of the various regional markets in which corporations operate, and the need for strategic adaptation and innovative solutions to offer products and services that meet their needs. This work provides guidelines for companies in the process of global expansion to develop target markets, marketing and competitive strategies based on a single concept.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of Uzbekistan’s textile industry is deemed a vital strategic priority for the nation. Uzbekistan is well-positioned to effectively process textile raw materials and produce high-value end products. However, in comparison to other textile-producing countries, the industry currently lags in technological advancement and attractiveness to foreign investors.

Foreign investment is essential for stimulating economic growth. To achieve sustained and robust economic development, it is crucial to draw capital into the economy. Given the ongoing trade tensions between the US and China, which are prompting factory relocations to Southeast Asian nations such as Vietnam, Cambodia, and Bangladesh, Uzbekistan has a distinct opportunity to leverage its textile clusters, extensive cotton production, and low labor and energy costs. This advantageous combination could attract many textile factories, potentially leading to billions of dollars in foreign direct investment and the creation of hundreds of thousands of jobs for the citizens of Uzbekistan.

The textile sector in Uzbekistan includes the production of various consumer goods, such as fabrics, threads, knitwear, cotton wool, and finished products. Since gaining independence in 1991, numerous enterprises have been established alongside the existing textile mills in Bukhara, Tashkent, Andijan, and Ferghana.

Additionally, textile enterprises associated with the Uztekstilprom Association export their products under the unified brand “Uztextile.” The previous monopoly on the sale of raw cotton to local manufacturers has also been lifted.

In support of the textile sector, the President endorsed the formation of the Uztekstilprom Association, leading to the dissolution of Uzbekengilsanoat JSC, which had previously served both regulatory and economic roles. This decision was made due to the outdated management system’s failure to adapt to modern trends in the textile industry and effectively support manufacturers.

The experiences of other countries have shown that establishing textile industry clusters is an effective development strategy. This model involves organizing a complete production cycle, from raw cotton cultivation to primary processing and the production of high-value textile products.

The President has also granted members of the Uztexstilprom Association various benefits and incentives, including a customs duty exemption until January 1, 2021, for imported cotton, synthetic fibers, wool, and other materials essential for textile production.

According to a document signed by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, starting with the next harvest, textile companies will, for the first time in Uzbekistan, be allowed to purchase raw cotton directly from farmers as part of an experimental initiative.

This innovation will enable textile producers to oversee the entire process of growing and harvesting cotton, from selecting varieties to setting quality standards for cotton fiber. For the first time, textile workers will also have the option to carry out the primary processing of raw cotton at their own or leased specialized facilities, or to outsource this process to ginneries on a reciprocal basis.

The "Uztexstilprom" association is a joint-stock company operating within the legal framework established by the Republic of Uzbekistan's laws on joint-stock companies and shareholder rights protection. The general meeting of shareholders acts as the highest governing body of the association, exercising its powers in accordance with the law. Uzbek textile products are exported to more than 55 countries around the globe. Key export markets include nations in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), especially Russia, as well as countries in Latin America, the European Union, South Korea, China, Singapore, Iran, Israel, and the United States, among others. In recent years, new markets have emerged, including Pakistan, Georgia, Croatia, Nigeria, and others. Russia and the CIS countries represent the largest importers of Uzbek textile goods, making up over 51% of total exports. Approximately 21% of exports are sent to South Asia, more than 12% to Europe, and 8% to the Middle East and Africa. In 2017, the export figures for textile, clothing, and knitwear products reached 1.3 billion US dollars.

Table 1. Forecast volumes of production of marketable products for 2018-2021 (billion sum).

№	Enterprises	2017y.	2018y.	2019 y.	2020 y.	2021 y.	Pace growth, %
1	Industrial production	10 87	12 41	4 269	16 553	19 201	116,0
	products at comparable prices,						
1.1	total by association	2 879,4	4 38,4	4 862,2	5 639,8	6 542,2	116,0
1.2.	including on:	7 688 8	202,4	9 668,0	10 913,0	12 658,7	116,0
	large enterprises						
	Small businesses	23	30,2	34,3	35,6	37,2	104,5
	including by:	688,5	1562,8	2 150,4	2 581,4	2 608,2	100,0

Table 1 indicates that in the past three years, a total of 92 industrial enterprises were established, with a combined investment of \$575.3 million and an export potential of \$215.8 million. These developments have created over 11,600 job opportunities. A significant highlight is the establishment of the Indorama Kokand Textile joint venture, which operates the Kokand Textile Plant and has an annual production capacity of 29,000 tons of yarn. Additionally, the Uzteks Group, in partnership with Swiss Capital, has opened a cotton yarn production facility in the Khorezm region, boasting an annual capacity of 12,000 tons.

To accelerate the growth of Uzbekistan's textile industry, enhance the production of high-quality competitive finished products, and promote these products in international markets, the following key reform areas should be pursued:

Increase the textile industry's contribution to the economy by boosting the volume and quality of textile products through a transition to high-tech production methods that offer competitive textiles with significant added value.

Revamp the management system of the textile industry by adopting advanced management technologies and effective support mechanisms for industry enterprises, addressing barriers to their development.

Continuously enhance the standardization and certification system in the textile sector to meet international standards, while modernizing and accrediting product testing laboratories.

Integrate advanced information and communication technologies in the industry to acquire reliable, timely information on domestic and international textile markets, conduct thorough analyses, and identify key development areas.

Implement a cluster development model that encompasses the entire production process, from raw cotton cultivation to primary processing, further processing at ginneries, and the production of high-value final textile products.

Ensure a balanced distribution of raw materials and establish new industry enterprises in conjunction with the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure. This includes building multifunctional transport and logistics hubs, optimizing transportation routes, and refining tariffs.

Encourage the adoption of innovative technologies, know-how, and design improvements in production processes. Promote the localization of modern fittings and accessories manufacturing to enhance the production and export of high-quality textile products and support national brands in global markets.

Significantly improve the training, retraining, and advanced education systems for textile industry personnel by expanding educational opportunities in popular specialties, updating curricula to reflect industry trends, intensifying research initiatives, and promoting international cooperation in education.

Approved "Roadmap" for the accelerated development of the textile and clothing and knitwear industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter - the "Roadmap").

The heads of ministries, departments and other organizations are personally responsible for the timely, complete and high-quality implementation of the measures provided for by the Roadmap.

Due to serious systemic problems in the industry, including the lack of effective management and the associated technological chain for the manufacture of finished products, the share of the textile sector in the structure of GDP is only 4.6% (data for the first half of this year). High monopolization and lack of due competition also hinder development and are the reason for the low profitability of raw cotton production, its processing and production of finished products.

Association Uztekstilprom works with marketing services at enterprises and its main function is to support domestic producers and create favorable conditions for the sale and export of finished products.

The main priorities in the work of the marketing department of the Uztekstilprom Association are:

Conducting an analysis of the economic activities of exporters in the interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan, development of road maps

Development of a production strategy at enterprises

Stimulation of production volumes using market levers

Import of textile products without overpricing.

Analysis of the information received from trading advisers in embassies, consulates.

Cooperation with ministries and departments, such as the Ministry of Foreign Trade, the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Finance, the State Tax Committee.

Working with the industry - opening new and promising markets for the sale of finished products, supporting domestic producers.

Analysis for the delivery of goods and the formation of a favorable environment for production.

Study and implementation of Western production technologies.

Reducing the tax burden for domestic producers.

Table 2. Importers of Turkish textile equipment of the association "Uztekstilprom".

№	Country	№	Country
1	Bangladesh	11	Russia
2	Iran	12	Turkmenistan
3	India	13	Bulgaria
4	Egypt	14	Vietnam
5	Pakistan	15	China
6	Uzbekistan	16	Ethiopia
7	USA	17	England
8	Germany	18	Poland
9	Belgium	19	Indonesia
10	Italy	20	Sudan

In 2015, the total export value of the Turkish textile machinery industry was 1.6 billion USD, and in 2019 it was 8.6 billion USD, an increase of almost 7 times during this period.

Based on the analysis conducted, several recommendations can be made to enhance the enterprise's strategy. For the primary activities of the Uztekstilprom association, a low-cost strategy is advisable,

emphasizing a more efficient utilization of fixed assets. Additionally, the management team should seek to establish relationships with new suppliers of raw materials and resources on more favorable terms for the company.

According to Porter's model, a differentiation strategy is suitable for a firm targeting a large market with both standard and innovative new products. Expanding the range of new materials would be advantageous for the Uztexstilprom association. Currently, most building products are in their maturity phase, so the firm should focus on sustaining its competitive edge (such as high quality and a well-considered discount system) for as long as possible.

The existing pricing strategy for the firm's products has been well-calibrated, resulting in significant profits. The decision to transform and modify products was also a sound choice to rejuvenate demand after market saturation. Introducing a new product modification will enable the company to regain high revenue and profit levels.

Therefore, in the short term, the company is advised to adopt a strategy focused on uncovering deeper customer needs, which could lead to an expanded market presence (for instance, through the production of new types of building structures).

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In modern conditions, the growth of global companies requires a multifaceted strategy, as different regional markets, competitor policies, and political and economic risks directly affect the development of the company. In this regard, the introduction of innovative technologies, working with different cultures, developing human resources, and accelerating the digital transformation process are considered to be the main factors of advantage. In particular, human capital and local cooperation, the provision of products and services that meet the requirements, as well as the flexible formulation of marketing strategies, play an important role in maintaining the pace of global growth. At the same time, a responsible approach to the environment, adherence to the principles of social responsibility, and sustainable development factors serve to strengthen competitive advantage.

The following are recommended to ensure strategic growth in the future:

1. Optimization of production and services through the wider introduction of digital ecosystems and innovative technologies;
2. Improving the skills of employees, encouraging creative ideas and startup projects, and strengthening cooperation in global teams;
3. Thorough study of international standards and regulations, establishment of specialized systems for assessing political and economic risks. These measures will create a basis for global companies to maintain a rapid competitive advantage and promote continuous innovative development.

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